

Modeling Systemic Climate Damage Interactions in an Input-Output Integrated Assessment Framework

Highlights

- Framework to represent environmental damages in input-output models
- Simulation of multiple climate damage scenarios in the MORDRED-IAM
- Climate impacts are found to slow down technological progress
- Importance of adverse climate change impacts on labor
- Scenarios integrating damages exhibit lower levels of economic growth and global warming

Abstract

We present a methodological framework to incorporating generic environmental damages in economic input-output models and apply the approach to the modeling of climate change impacts in an integrated assessment model, considering potential adverse climate impacts on capital, labor, and land. We simulate multiple climate damage scenarios and compare them with a reference pathway to examine economy–climate feedbacks and interactions across damage types. Incorporating climate impacts substantially alters 21st-century economic output, emission and temperature trajectories, generally reducing world output while moderating global temperature increases in scenarios that include all parametrized damages. Assumptions regarding future labor productivity developments and the severity of adverse climate impacts significantly influence simulation outcomes, with endogenously changing labor productivities and higher impact severity being linked to an earlier peak of world output and a lower degree of climate change. Climate impacts are found to slow down improvements in the greenhouse gas intensity of economic activities, while climate-change-induced increases in land intensities can elevate emissions from land-use changes. Higher rates of capital depreciation may paradoxically stimulate economic activity while lowering consumption. Labor-related damages exert the strongest individual effect on economic development; however, the combination of output-, capital-, and labor-related damages results in a strong, non-linear effect on world economic output absent in scenarios that only feature isolated damage types. Thus, assessing climate damages in isolation can substantially underestimate their systemic effects on both economic activity and emissions.

Keywords

Climate change damages; input-output models; Integrated Assessment Models; climate change scenarios; system dynamics; global environmental change

1. Introduction

The quantitative modeling of damages on the global economy resulting from environmental degradation and the transgression of planetary boundaries supports the design of effective and efficient policies and informs the emerging legal ‘loss and damage’ framework under the UNFCCC [1], [2]. Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs)—such as optimal growth models, computable general equilibrium models (CGEMs), energy-system models, or macroeconomic models [3] have a decades-long history of projecting economic climate impacts and currently dominate quantitative climate change research [4]. Although these IAMs differ in structure and employ various methods to estimate adverse economic impacts, they generally rely on damage functions that vary with changes in global mean temperature [5], [6].

Complementing these established IAM types, a growing number of quantitative models have been developed to represent interactions among environmental, economic, and energy systems and the resulting economic damages. These models are built with alternative economic theories and modeling techniques such as stock-flow consistent models [7], [8], system dynamics models [9], [10], [11] or life-cycle impact assessment (LCIA) models [12]. These alternative IAMs provide valuable insights by examining climate-related financial risks, mineral and energy resources as well as non-climate damages.

The rise of new IAMs departing from neoclassical climate economics assumptions can also be explained by the methodological weaknesses underpinning damage assessments in frequently used IAMs—such as DICE, FUND or PAGE— which continue to shape policy development [13]. Criticisms include the insufficient consideration of epistemic, ethical and political dimensions of uncertainty in IAM-based modeling exercises [14]; a lack of genuine complexity within the models; the use of discount rates and overly optimistic assumptions regarding technological development [15]; the neglect of climate tipping points, the assumption that economic sectors not exposed to the weather are unaffected by climate change, and methodological inconsistencies in the estimation and representation of damages [13]. This results in damage assessments predicting only a 5.3 – 13.8% GDP loss at 7.4 –8.6 °C of global warming relative to the pre-industrial period [5], which stands in stark contrast to scientists’ dire warnings of a climate emergency [16] and the numerous already observable and projected losses and damages enumerated by the IPCC’s WG II [17]. Even with updated damage parameters, the FUND model still estimates losses of only 2.82% of GDP in 2100 under a business-as-usual scenario [18].

This paper seeks to address some of the current methodological issues in modeling environmental damages to economic structures while contributing to the dynamically expanding field of non-neoclassical IAMs. It does so by modeling and exploring climate change damages in the MORDRED model, an IAM of medium complexity built on environmentally and socially extended input-output data [19]. Although the potential of combining environmentally extended input-output analysis [20] with integrated assessment modeling for studying multi-dimensional sustainability impacts, demand-side solutions and post-growth climate mitigation scenarios has been recognized [21], to the best of our knowledge, no IAM has yet been developed that draws on holistic input-output-based damage modeling.

Accordingly, this work pursues three research objectives:

- (1) the development of a new methodological framework that facilitates the systematic representation of environmental impacts in input-output models;
- (2) the application of this framework to model climate damages within an IAM; and

(3) the simulation of different ‘damage scenarios’ and the analysis of key model dynamics.

In line with these objectives, the remainder of this article is structured as follows: in the next section, we introduce the new framework for the representation of environmental impacts in input-output models and describe its application to the incorporation of climate damages in MORDRED. Subsequently, we explore the resulting model dynamics through a scenario simulation exercise. We conclude by discussing the merits and the limits of our approach, and by outlining directions for future work.

2. Methodology

2.1. Representation of damages in an input-output framework

In input-output (IO) modeling, economic processes are represented by Leontief production functions, which are characterized by the strict non-substitutability of productive factors [22]. In other words, the production of one unit of any good requires a fixed combination of inputs, and no factor can be reduced by increasing the use of another. For instance, labor cannot be substituted for capital, nor can materials be substituted by labor. Within this framework, technological change is represented as variations in the quantity of inputs required per unit of output. At any given point in time, however, the parameters of the production function remain fixed, and the condition of non-substitutability continues to hold.

In a multisectoral economy, the parameters of the Leontief production function can be expressed through a matrix and a set of intensity vectors:

- Input–output matrix (A matrix): each column indicates the quantity of inputs from each sector required to produce one unit of output in the corresponding sector.
- Labor intensity vector: each element represents the amount of labor necessary to produce one unit of sectoral output.
- Capital intensity vector: each element corresponds to the necessary stock of capital to produce one unit of sectoral output.

In an environmentally extended IO framework, biophysical input factors also enter the production function as intensity vectors. For example, a land (water, material, ...) intensity vector denotes the amount of land (water, material, ...) required to generate one unit of sectoral output. Equally, a pollution intensity vector contains information on the amount of pollution generated per unit of sectoral output.

Consequently, in an IO framework, adverse impacts from global environmental change can be represented via variations in (i) the intensities of intermediate or primary inputs (labor, capital, land, ...), and (ii) the available stock of primary inputs.

When damages alter input intensities, greater quantities of inputs are required to produce the same unit of output. For example, as mineral deposits and fossil resources become depleted, the extraction of a given quantity of material requires more inputs, which amounts to a change in the columns of the A matrix that represent the extraction sectors. Depending on the extraction method, the same process may also require more labor which would result in a change in the labor intensity vector. Likewise, additional machinery or capital stock may be needed, increasing the values of the capital intensity vector. Equally, declining soil productivity leads to a higher land demand per unit of agricultural output, i.e. a change in the land intensity vector. Thus,

increases in input intensities can be interpreted as an environmentally induced reversal of technological progress.

Alternatively, adverse environmental impacts may affect the availability of primary inputs. For labor, this can occur through two channels: a reduction in the number of workers (due to incapacity or mortality) or a reduction in working time, since total labor supply in a given period is the product of the number of workers and the hours worked. For capital, damages take the form of destruction of capital stock within a given sector, either as a discrete loss linked to a specific period of time, or as an increase in depreciation. Capital destruction in the aftermath of a flood would exemplify the former, while a reduction in the useful life of equipment due to extreme temperatures would manifest as a higher depreciation rate. For land, damages correspond to a reduction in the stock of land available for productive purposes.

Last, a part of sectoral output itself can be lost due to environmental impacts, which is modeled as an indirect increase in the factor intensity of production.

Table 1 summarizes the relevant variables in an IO model that change in response to environmental damages.

Variable	Unit
<i>Input-output matrix A</i>	€/€
<i>Labor intensity vector</i>	h/€
<i>Capital intensity vector</i>	€·year/€
<i>Environmental intensity vector (land, material, energy...)</i>	(ha, kt, EJ...)-year/€
<i>Working time</i>	h/(worker·year)
<i>Labor force</i>	workers
<i>Capital stock</i>	€
<i>Environmental stocks (land, resources...)</i>	ha, kt, ...

Table 1: Key variables within an input-output framework affected by environmental damages.

2.2. Realization in MORDRED

We applied the methodological framework to MORDRED (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development) because the representation of the world economy in this model draws heavily on IO data and includes all relevant variables listed in Table 1.

2.2.1. Model summary

Mordred is a system dynamics model that represents broad socio-economic dynamics at a global scale and their relationship with the environment. The model consists of several coupled modules that focus on specific aspects of the world system such as demographic and economic developments as well as the consequences of the former on the demand for, and supply of, labor, land and energy, and on material extraction, pollution and the climate system.

The demographic module projects the evolution of the world population, which is divided into three regions: the center (i.e. the high-income countries), semi-periphery (upper-middle-income countries), and periphery (lower-middle- and low-income countries). Demographic changes are driven by birth and death rates, which are mainly influenced by per capita consumption levels across different regions and social classes within MORDRED. The demographic module also accounts for populations living in subsistence conditions at the margins of the global economy.

For each world region, migration between the subsistence and the world economy is modeled as a function of the difference in consumption between the poorest class and the subsistence class.

The economic module calculates the volume of goods and services produced in the economy and their distribution across regions and social classes. For the former it uses an IO framework in which the global economy is divided into 25 sectors, including the food, industry, services and mineral extraction sector, as well as different energy sectors. For the latter, in every world region, the population living outside the subsistence regime is divided into three social classes: The wealthiest 20%, the poorest 30% and the middle 50%.

For its calculations, the model relies on exogenously defined desired growth rates in per capita consumption for each class and region. Government consumption is defined as a fixed percentage of household consumption, while investment evolves endogenously as a function of the quantity of capital goods required for production. During the model simulation, actual output of goods and services may not match demand, as the former is constrained by the availability of labor, energy, labor and land.

The labor module projects the changes in the available workforce that depend on changes in the demographic module and imposes an upper limit on production capacity while the energy module calculates the total energy demanded by the system and tracks the increasing depletion of fossil resources. The land module compares land demand with supply and allocates available land between different land uses. Availability of land is primarily driven by land intensities.

The climate module is a greatly simplified and adapted version of the climate model contained in the WILIAM-IAM [23]. It calculates changes in the carbon cycle and in global average temperatures as a consequence of different greenhouse gas emission pathways.

An exhaustive description of MORDRED is available in Lauer & Llases [24]. A GitHub repository [25] provides information on different model versions and the 25 sectors of the model that were aggregated from EXIOBASE3 [19].

2.2.2. Introduction of climate damages

We applied the methodological framework to the representation of climate change damages.

In the model, climate impacts evolve as functions of global average temperature change relative to the pre-industrial (1850) period.

$$\Delta Temp = Temp(t) - Temp(1850) \quad (1)$$

We include potential climate damages in the economic, labor and land module.

In the economy module, capital stock and intensity are assumed to be affected by climate-change-induced increases in extreme weather events and sea-level rise.

Extreme weather events including droughts, floods, storms, wildfires and heatwaves are assumed to increase the depreciation rate of the capital stock in all sectors as global average temperature rises. A minimum and a maximum estimate for the annual global damage in capital stock at 4 °C degree of warming was made based on damage estimates for the US in the period 2010-2019 [26] and for Europe in the period 1981-2020 [27] as well as projected increases in the intensity and frequency of extreme weather events given in IPCC WGI's contribution to the sixth assessment report [28]. Possible higher impacts of heatwaves [29] and droughts [30] in

world regions outside the US and Europe, as well as the non-linear effects of compound extreme weather events were taken into account through adjustment factors. The resulting damage range represents losses in a hypothetical world with 4°C of global warming and the capital stock of the USA in 2015. To distinguish between impacts in different sectors, the 25 sectors in MORDRED were categorized into 'high-exposure' sectors particularly affected by extreme weather impacts (such as the food, transportation and energy sectors [31], [32]) and 'low-exposure' sectors. 70% of the overall damage at 4 °C of global warming is assumed to affect all sectors while the rest of the damage is assumed to be concentrated in high-exposure sectors.

The ratio between capital stock lost at 4 °C of warming and total capital stock constitutes the additional extreme-weather-induced capital depreciation for each sector, with $\alpha_i = 0$ for the low-exposure sectors and 1 for the high-exposure sectors (2) (3). The lower and upper bound estimates for total damages result in a low and a high depreciation estimate.

$$\delta_i^{4^\circ C, min} = 0.7 \cdot \frac{Total\ damages_{min}}{\sum_{i=1}^{25} K_{US2015\ i}} + \alpha_i \cdot 0.3 \frac{Total\ damages_{min}}{\sum K_{US2015\ high\ exposure}} \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_i^{4^\circ C, max} = 0.7 \cdot \frac{Total\ damages_{max}}{\sum_{i=1}^{25} K_{US2015\ i}} + \alpha_i \cdot 0.3 \frac{Total\ damages_{max}}{\sum K_{US2015\ high\ exposure}} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta_i^{extreme_weather} = \delta_i^{4^\circ C} \cdot \left(\frac{(\Delta Temp - 1)^2}{9} \right) \quad (4)$$

Under a high emission scenario and/or antarctic instability, 4 - 7 % of the global population could live in areas flooded annually by the end of the century [33], [34]. We assume that population is directly correlated to the size of the capital stock, and that capital assets are more concentrated in coastal areas (e.g. ports, refineries etc.). Thus, we assume that 6 - 9% of the global capital assets could be threatened by annual flooding under a temperature increase of 4 °C. Additionally, we assume that half of the capital stock can be protected by hard coastal protection while the other half is lost due to a managed retreat of the population. This leads to an overall loss of 3 - 4.5% of global capital stock as global warming approaches the 4°C mark. Since these losses do not repeat after the population has resettled and new capital stock has been constructed elsewhere, sea-level-rise-induced losses are modeled as discrete events when certain temperature thresholds are exceeded (2°C, 3°C, and 4°C), following a Gaussian function and affecting all sectors' depreciation rates equally (5).

The additional costs linked to the construction of coastal protection is represented in the model as additional GFCF in the construction sector, which is contained in sector 5 and is estimated based on Hinkel et al. [33], considering the fact that a loss of coral reef protection due to temperature changes higher than 1.5 °C to 2 °C doubles the exposure of built capital and people to flooding [35] and assuming that the coastal protection has to be renewed once during the model simulation.

The overall effect of climate impacts on depreciation in a given sector and moment of time is obtained by adding the impacts from extreme weather events and sea-level-rise (6).

$$\delta_i^{slr} = \beta 0^{2^\circ C_slr} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{(t-10-t^{2^\circ C})^2}{\beta 1^{2^\circ C_slr}}\right)} + \beta 0^{3^\circ C_slr} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{(t-10-t^{3^\circ C})^2}{\beta 1^{3^\circ C_slr}}\right)} + \beta 0^{4^\circ C_slr} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{(t-10-t^{4^\circ C})^2}{\beta 1^{4^\circ C_slr}}\right)} \quad (5)$$

$$\delta_i^{climate\ change} = \delta_i^{extreme\ weather} + \delta_i^{slr} \quad (6)$$

Climate-change-induced increases in input coefficients are only considered for the agricultural sector, which is contained in MORDRED sector 1. We estimate the hypothetical share of output that is destroyed due to adverse effects of insect pests [36] and heat [37] for 4 °C of warming (7) which leads to an increase in the capital intensity without damage ($Int_1^{k,wod}$) (8) and increases the intensity of intermediate goods. The latter is modeled through multiplying the column in the A matrix corresponding to sector 1 with a factor α_{loss} (9), (10), (11).

$$X_{loss_1} = (\alpha_{insects}^{4^\circ C} + \alpha_{heat}^{4^\circ C}) \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta Temp - 1}{3} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$Int_1^k = \frac{Int_1^{k,wod}}{(1 - X_{loss_1})} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{loss}^{4^\circ C} = \frac{1}{1 - X_{loss_1}} \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_{loss} = \beta 0_{loss} + \beta 1_{loss} \cdot \Delta Temp + \beta 2_{loss} \cdot \Delta Temp^2 \quad (10)$$

$$a_{i,1} = a_{i,1} \cdot \alpha_{loss} \quad (11)$$

In the labor module, the maximum supply of labor hours depends on the size of the population that belongs to the global economy and is in the working age, the participation rate (Prt_r) and the annual working hours per person (12). Although the methodological framework contains the possibility of a reduction of the working force through environmental impacts, we assume no *direct* climate-change-induced changes in mortality rates, e.g. through the spread of vector- or water-borne diseases or the increase in natural disasters, given that the actual effect of those factors on mortality are strongly mediated by the socio-economic context [38], [39]. However, we assume that annual working hours can be negatively affected by increases in deadly heat. The share of working hours lost due to heat-related damage (HD^{Max_Lb}) depends on the share of days with deadly heat at 4°C of warming, estimated based on Mora et al. [40], as well as on the assumed share of workers whose ability to work is affected due to the deadly heat conditions (13).

$$Max_Lb = Pop_{15-64\ years} \cdot Prt_r \cdot \frac{annual\ working\ hours}{worker} \cdot (1 - HD^{Max_Lb}) \quad (12)$$

$$HD^{Max_Lb} = \frac{days_{deadly\ heat}}{days_{year}} \cdot \frac{workers_{affected}}{workers} \cdot \left(\frac{(\Delta Temp - 1)^2}{9} \right) \quad (13)$$

Additionally, we assume that global warming adversely affects labor productivity. Dasgupta et al. [41] find that for 3 °C of warming global effective labor, including both productivity and hours worked, decreases by 18% ($\alpha_{Lprod_{low}}$) for low-exposure and by 25% ($\alpha_{Lprod_{high}}$) for high exposure activities. Low-exposure working conditions are defined as work outside in the shade or indoors while high-exposure working conditions are defined as works outside with no shade. The MORDRED sectors were classified as having predominantly low- or high-exposure working conditions, resulting in sectors 1, 4 and 5 (food, mining, industry) being linked to high exposure

and the rest of the sectors to low exposure. Here, for simplicity, we assume that the losses apply solely to labor productivity. Thus, the sector and temperature dependent heat-related damage to labor productivity ($HD_i^{Lb_prod}$) is calculated according to equation (14) and (15). This damage factor leads to an increase in the original sectoral labor intensity without damage ($Int_i^{Lb,wod}$) (16). In sector 1, the destroyed output further increases the labor intensity (17) while in sector 3 and 8 an extraction difficulty factor (Edf) related to the depletion of fossil resources leads to a higher labor intensity as resources become more difficult to access (18).

$$HD_{i=high\ exposure\ sectors}^{Lb_prod} = \alpha_{Lprod_{high}} \cdot \left(\frac{(\Delta Temp - 1)^2}{4} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$HD_{i=low\ exposure\ sectors}^{Lb_prod} = \alpha_{Lprod_{low}} \cdot \left(\frac{(\Delta Temp - 1)^2}{4} \right) \quad (15)$$

$$Int_i^{Lb} = \frac{Int_i^{Lb,wod}}{(1 - HD_i^{Lb_prod})} \quad (16)$$

$$Int_1^{Lb} = \frac{Int_1^{Lb,wod}}{(1 - X_{loss_1} - HD_1^{Lb_prod})} \quad (17)$$

$$Int_{3,8}^{Lb} = \frac{Int_{3,8}^{Lb,wod}}{(1 - HD_{3,8}^{Lb_prod})} \cdot Edf \quad (18)$$

For damages in the land model, we account for land losses due to sea-level rise, river floods, temperature and humidity change, based on estimates found in the literature [33], [42], [43], [44] (19). These damages reduce the amount of habitable land that can be used for economic purposes (20). In sector 1, there is an increase in the intensity of agricultural land use (21). Lastly, it is assumed that rising temperatures and the increasing severity and frequency of extreme weather events linearly reduce the number of people that can be sustained per unit of land in the subsistence regime. This is modeled as an additional intensity factor added to the original subsistence land intensity without damages (22), (23).

$$Land_loss = \beta_{SLR,floods,temp,humidty}^{land_loss} \cdot \left(\frac{(\Delta Temp - 1)^2}{9} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$Disponible_Land = Disponible_{Land}^{wod} - Land_loss \quad (20)$$

$$Int_{agr.land}^{Land} = \frac{Int_{agr.land}^{Land,wod}}{(1 - X_{loss_1})} \quad (21)$$

$$Extra_Int_{sub_land}^{Land} = \beta^{Extra_Int_Land_sub} \cdot (\Delta Temp - 1) \quad (22)$$

$$Int_{sub_land}^{Land} = Int_{sub_land}^{Land,wod} + Extra_Int_{sub_land}^{Land} \quad (23)$$

The Supplementary Material (SM) contains the numerical values for all estimated damage parameters.

2.3. Scenario design

We develop a baseline scenario projecting economic development without climate change impacts, and a set of damage scenarios demonstrating how various forms of climate damage modify the baseline trajectory.

To render the scenarios comparable the values for scenario and model parameters are the same in all scenarios, except for damage-relevant parameters. The common scenario assumptions include (1) low per capita growth rates for social classes in high-income countries and medium per capita growth rates for social classes in the rest of the world; (2) low energy intensity improvements in production processes; (3) a moderate increase in capital intensity; (4) fast declines in land intensities; (5) moderate substitution of fossil energy through renewable energy types. Rather optimistic assumptions regarding land productivity improvements and fossil energy availability, coupled with rather pessimistic assumptions regarding the energy transition and future declines in greenhouse gas intensities, provide a suitable framework to focus on the economy-climate nexus because they tend to generate medium to high-emission pathways that are less affected by potential land scarcity issues, and thus, result in higher temperature changes and higher observable impacts. This approach addresses our main research objective, i.e. to assess the influence of parameterized damage factors on economic development pathways in the model. Section 2 SM contains more information on the scenarios' boundary conditions.

The simulated damage scenarios can be categorized according to the *type* of impacts they incorporate, the *severity* of the adverse impacts, and the *evolution of sectoral labor productivity*.

First, we construct three damage categories: category 'A' includes damages related to sea-level rise and land-related damages; category 'B' includes impacts on labor productivities and supply; category 'C' includes impacts on economic production, i.e. input coefficients and capital stock. From these categories we construct 7 types of damage scenarios: A, B, C, A+B, A+C, B+C, A+B+C. We are primarily interested in the dynamics produced by the last type of damage scenarios and use scenarios with a partial representation of damages primarily to compare the strength of, and interactions between, different types of damages.

Second, we distinguish between three severity levels of impact: moderate, low and high, with moderate impacts reflecting our best guess for every damage parameter. To derive the values for a lower severity, we decrease the damage factors pertaining to category 'B' by 30%, and the damage factors pertaining to category 'A' and 'C' by 25%. For a higher severity of impacts, we increase the damage factors pertaining to category 'B' by 20%, and the damage factors pertaining to 'A' and 'C' by 25%, except for the increased depreciation rate, which is increased by 42%, reflecting our higher-end estimate related to the loss of capital stock.

Finally, the evolution of sectoral labor productivities in the damage scenarios can be purely exogenous, reflecting social learning and technological innovations happening over time, or complemented by an endogenous component. To fix an exogenous target for labor productivity improvements, we take the labor productivity (and intensity) levels of the center in 2019, given in EXIOBASE3, as reference levels because they constitute an example for empirically observed high labor productivity values. Thus, by 2100, in scenarios with purely exogenous labor productivity developments, global average productivity levels are assumed to have increased to 70% of the reference productivity levels. Conversely, in scenarios in which productivity levels are influenced by endogenous model developments, the exogenous target level is set to only 30% of the reference productivity levels. However, those scenarios also contain a labor intensity multiplier that changes labor intensities as an exponentially falling function of global average consumption. The parameters of the function are selected to reduce labor intensities by 80% when the global average consumption has reached the average consumption of the center in 2019. Thus, in a scenario with strong economic growth, the endogenous component makes labor productivities increase faster than in scenarios without this component. However, given that

climate impacts can affect both labor productivities and economic output levels, the endogenization of labor productivities also acts as a potential amplifier of economic damages.

By simulating every type of damage scenario with low, moderate and high climate impacts, and with, as well as without, endogenously evolving labor productivity levels, we build our scenario set, which contains a total of 43 scenarios (Table 2). All scenarios were simulated for the period 2019–2100 using MORDRED version 1.0.6.

<i>Scenario simulation</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Severity</i>	<i>Endogenous component in labor intensity changes</i>
1 (<i>Baseline</i>)	<i>none</i>	-	<i>yes</i>
2	<i>ABC</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
3			<i>yes</i>
4		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
5			<i>yes</i>
6			<i>no</i>
7		<i>yes</i>	
8		<i>A</i>	<i>low</i>
9	<i>yes</i>		
10	<i>moderate</i>		<i>no</i>
11			<i>yes</i>
12			<i>no</i>
13	<i>yes</i>		
14	<i>B</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
15			<i>yes</i>
16		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
17			<i>yes</i>
18			<i>no</i>
19		<i>yes</i>	
20	<i>C</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
21			<i>yes</i>
22		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
23			<i>yes</i>
24			<i>no</i>
25		<i>yes</i>	
26	<i>AB</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
27			<i>yes</i>
28		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
29			<i>yes</i>
30			<i>no</i>
31		<i>yes</i>	
32	<i>AC</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
33			<i>yes</i>
34		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
35			<i>yes</i>
36			<i>high</i>

37			<i>yes</i>
38	<i>BC</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>no</i>
39			<i>yes</i>
40		<i>moderate</i>	<i>no</i>
41			<i>yes</i>
42		<i>high</i>	<i>no</i>
43			<i>yes</i>

Table 2: Overview of scenario simulations.

3. Results

This section contains the simulation results of selected scenarios that allow us to show key model dynamics resulting from the introduction of different types of climate impacts. We begin by analyzing damage scenarios that integrate all parameterized damages from the economic, labor, and land modules (type ABC scenarios), and subsequently examine the effects of each damage type in isolation

3.1. Economy-climate interactions

In the baseline scenario both world output and global warming rise strongly until the end of the 21st century, reaching more than 450 trillion 2019-€ and more than 3.6 °C despite the assumed changes in the energy infrastructure (Figure 1).¹ However, once damages of all types (A+B+C) are introduced, the observed dynamics change significantly.

In scenarios with endogenously evolving labor productivities, world output peaks between 2045 and 2060 and decreases afterwards, being between 2.9 and 3.6 times lower than in the baseline by 2100 (Figure 1c). In scenarios without endogenously evolving labor productivities, economic growth comes to a halt as well, albeit about 2 decades later. World output begins to decline moderately but persistently after 2075 (2080) in scenarios with high (moderate) impacts. Conversely, the difference in output between the peak in 2082 and output in 2100 in the low-impact scenario is marginal. By 2100 world output levels in scenarios without an endogenous labor productivity component are between 27% and 49% lower than in the baseline (Figure 1d).

While world output trajectories of all scenarios, including the baseline, are comparable until 2045, from 2040 onward, global temperature trajectories rise faster than in the baseline scenario in all damage scenarios (Figure 1a-b). However, in the second half of the simulation this dynamic reverses for most of the damage scenarios: after 2065, 2070 and 2080, in scenarios with endogenously evolving labor productivities and high, moderate and low impacts, temperatures in the baseline scenario rise significantly faster. As a result, by the end of the simulation, increases in global average temperature are projected to range from 2.99 °C to 3.25 °C, depending on the severity of impacts. Scenarios lacking an endogenous labor productivity component exhibit similar dynamics, albeit with a temporal delay. In the high-impact scenario, average temperature increases more rapidly than in the moderate- and low-

¹ The baseline scenario was simulated with endogenously changing labor productivity. However, the limits to growth in this baseline are sufficiently weak that a scenario with purely exogenous changes would produce comparable results. Consequently, we employ the same baseline throughout as a benchmark for comparison with the damage scenarios. The only variable exhibiting notable differences between baselines with and without endogenous labor productivity is total labor demand.

impact scenarios between 2040 and 2060. After 2060, this trend reverses, and by the final decade of the simulation, the rate of warming has slowed enough for average global temperatures to fall below those observed in the baseline scenario. The scenario with moderate impacts reaches its turning point in 2099, while the scenario with low impact displays higher degrees of warming than the baseline beyond the 21st century. In the final year of the simulation, global warming is 3.56 °C in the high-impact, 3.64 °C in the moderate-impact and 3.76 °C in the low-impact scenario. Unsurprisingly, in both types of scenarios, the lower the adverse impacts from global warming, the longer the global economy grows, resulting in higher final output levels, higher emissions and higher changes in global average temperature.

Thus, temperature and output pathways can differ significantly, depending on assumptions about the evolution of labor productivity and the severity of impacts, with endogenously changing productivities and higher impact severity being linked to an earlier peak of world output and a lower degree of climate change. At the same time, multiple economy-climate interactions can be observed across all scenarios. Taking into account the feedback effect of the climate system on the economic system produces a strong deviation from the historical trend of continuous economic expansion, and a more dynamic variation in the rate of global warming. Interestingly, in all but one scenario, the introduction of climate impacts ultimately results in a lower scale of warming.

As our scenario design features very low consumption growth rates for the social classes of the world region 'center', simulation results with higher growth rates in the center are displayed in Suppl. Figure 1. While output and temperature change are higher in the baseline scenario, the dynamics observed in the damage scenarios are comparable to those just discussed.

Figure 1: Change of global average temperature with respect to 1850 in the Baseline (grey), high-impact (blue), moderate-impact (yellow) and low-impact (green) scenarios with (a) and without (b) endogenously (b) evolving labor productivities. World output trajectory in the Baseline, high-impact, moderate-impact and low-impact scenarios with endogenously (c) and exogenously (d) evolving labor productivities. All damage scenarios belong to the type 'ABC'.

The differences in the rate of temperature change observed in Figure 1 can be explained by changes in total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and GHG intensities (Figure 2) occurring during the simulation period. The pattern of total GHG emissions in the simulated scenarios is roughly correlated with the evolution of world output. GHG emissions peak first between 2040 and 2050 in the high- and moderate-damage scenarios, independent from the type of labor productivity development (Figure 2a, d), followed by peaks between 2055 and 2075 for the low-damage scenarios. The peaks in total emissions do not correspond to the peaks in total output because they are driven by the conversion of forest into land used for the generation of food, energy, and infrastructure. Interestingly, in the baseline, emissions rise continuously but more smoothly than in the damage scenarios, indicating the absence of major land use conversions. The differences in the observed patterns are produced mainly due to a climate-change-induced increase in the intensity of agricultural land in the damage scenarios which lead to a higher land demand, and thus, higher pressure to convert non-economically used forests than in the baseline scenario. As output and land demands remain high for a longer time in scenarios with purely exogenously evolving labor productivities, those scenarios exhibit higher land pressure and higher emissions from land use changes. Nevertheless, total GHG emissions ultimately decline across all damage scenarios and are 22.2% to 69.4% lower than in the baseline scenarios at the end of the simulation. In the low-impact damage scenario without an endogenous labor productivity component, emissions by 2100 have not declined enough to lower global average

temperatures below baseline levels; however, the trend indicates that the turning point is approaching.

The GHG emissions that are not related to land use changes are driven by the scale of production and consumption as well as by the respective GHG intensities (Figure 2b, c, e, f). GHG intensities of output are comparable between scenarios with and without an endogenous labor productivity component and are the highest for scenarios with a high severity of impacts. Thus, interestingly, climate damages slow down technological progress. Nevertheless, the trend of falling GHG intensities of economic production processes are not reversed in any damage scenario. Conversely, for private (household) and public (government) consumption the effect of climate impacts on GHG intensity is so significant that in the high-impact scenario without endogenous labor productivity component the improvement in the GHG intensity of consumption comes to a halt in 2091 and subsequently starts to increase, which amounts to another break with historical trends (Figure 2f).

Although GHG intensities are significantly lower in the baseline scenario the divergence in the scale of global production and consumption between the baseline and the damage scenarios by far offsets the difference in intensities, resulting in declining total emissions in the damage scenarios, and increasing emissions in the baseline during the second half of the simulation.

Figure 2: a) Total GHG emissions in CO₂ equivalents, b) GHG intensity of output, c) GHG intensity of consumption in the Baseline (grey), high-impact (blue), moderate-impact (yellow) and low-impact (green) scenarios with endogenously evolving labor productivities; d) total GHG emissions in CO₂ equivalents, e) GHG intensity of output, f) GHG intensity of consumption without endogenously evolving labor productivities. All damage scenarios belong to the type 'ABC'.

3.2. Interactions between different climate damage types

Comparing the evolution of world output in scenarios that only consider some types of damages (A, B, C) with scenarios incorporating various or all parametrized damages (AB, AC, BC, ABC) shows the strength of isolated and combined climate change impacts in the model (Figure 3).

Damage scenarios of type A, which capture only sea-level-rise- and land-related damages, closely track the baseline scenario irrespective of the severity of impacts. Conversely, the incorporation of labor-related damages alone (damage type B) is sufficient to halt economic growth in all scenarios and reverse it in all but the low-impact-non-endogenous-labor-productivity scenario (Figure 3e). In general, scenarios of type B produce patterns similar to scenarios of type ABC but with a temporal delay, resulting in higher output peaks. In scenarios with an endogenous labor productivity component the difference in output between scenarios of type B and of type ABC has reduced considerably, especially in the case of high and moderate impacts. Conversely, in scenarios without an endogenous labor productivity component output remains significantly higher in scenarios of type 'B', especially in the moderate and high-impact scenarios. The similarity in the patterns produced by the scenarios of type B and ABC indicate the important role of labor-related damages in shaping model outcomes. Scenarios with capital- and output-related damages (type C) differ significantly between scenarios with moderate (Figure 3a,d), weak (Figure 3b,e) and high impacts (Figure 3c,f). In scenarios with moderate impacts, the output trajectory closely resembles the baseline trajectory during the great majority of the simulation period. Interestingly, in scenarios with low impacts, the presence of damages increases the growth rate of global economic production, resulting in a significantly higher output in type-C scenarios than in the baseline scenario (526 trillion € compared to 463 trillion €). Likewise, final demand is higher in the damage scenarios. However, when disaggregating final demand into investment and consumption, we find that total consumption is slightly lower in the damage scenarios and the higher final demand is explained by higher gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) necessary due to higher capital depreciation rates from climate change impacts (Figure 4a, b). Likewise, the ratio of final demand to total output declines slightly during the simulation for the damage type-C scenarios, indicating a damage-induced increase in the production of intermediate goods. Thus, type-C scenarios illustrate the possibility of climate damages leading to an increase in economic growth but a decrease in consumption. Consequently, the assumption that an increase in production is linked to an increase in consumption might no longer hold under climate change scenarios. In type-C scenarios with high impacts the output trajectory starts to diverge from the baseline from 2060 onward. In the scenario with an endogenous labor component impacts are sufficiently strong to cause output to peak and decline (Figure 3c) while in the scenario lacking the endogenous development output increases until the end of the simulation albeit at a lower rate than in the baseline (Figure 3f). These findings point to a relatively high sensitivity of capital- and output-related damages to the assumed severity of impacts.

Combining the damages of type A and B, we find that labor-related damages strongly dominate over sea-level-rise and land-related damages since the type-AB output trajectory closely resembles the type-B trajectory, as illustrated by the blue diamonds (type B) and the red diamonds (type AB) in Figure 3. Likewise, the trajectory resulting from the combination of type-A and type-C damages clearly is influenced to a stronger degree by damage type C. Nevertheless, the trajectory in the AC scenarios differs from the trajectories of scenarios that contain only one type of damage: for moderate- and high-impact scenarios, the resulting growth rate is lower than in the type-A and the type-C scenarios; for low-impact scenarios, world output grows faster than in the type-A scenarios but slower than in the type-C scenarios. Last, BC scenarios closely resemble ABC scenarios, with the combined effect of labor-, capital- and output-related damage factors imposing an earlier decline and reversal of economic growth. This finding is not sensitive to (exogenous vs. endogenous) labor productivity assumptions. Thus, compared to capital-, output- and labor-related damages, in our scenario parametrization, sea-level-rise- and land-

related damages are relatively minor, while the interaction effect between damages in the economic and in the labor model significantly alter the simulation results.

Figure 3: Evolution of world output in scenarios with (a-c) and without (d-f) endogenously evolving labor productivities and moderate (a, d), low (b, e) and high (c, f) impacts. a-f) Baseline (grey (dashed) line), scenarios with damage type A (red dots), type B (blue diamond), type C (black star), type AB (red diamond), type AC (red star), type BC (blue star), type ABC (yellow, green or blue (dashed) line).

3.2. Impacts on damages on economic production factors

Figure 4 shows different impacts of climate damages on variables related to the economic production process. As already discussed in the previous section, in type-C damage scenarios investment increases faster than in the baseline because the loss of capital stock alone does not stop economic growth but rather results in an increase in the production of capital goods to meet rising consumption demands. In type-B scenarios GFCF first exceeds investment in the ABC-type scenarios due to the higher output levels but, as output begins to decline, drops below the GFCF levels in the ABC-type scenarios because the B-type scenarios do not consider a climate-change-induced increase in capital depreciation.

Comparing ABC-type scenarios with and without an endogenous labor productivity component with the baseline we find that the annual total depreciation of capital stock increases faster in scenarios with climate impacts. In scenarios with a strong decline in output, total depreciation eventually decreases modestly, while in scenarios with a moderate decline in output total depreciation first stabilizes but then continues to increase slightly. In the scenario with purely exogenously driven labor productivities and low impacts total depreciation is still higher than in the baseline scenario in the final year of the simulation (Figure 4c). The share of the food sector's depreciation in total depreciation is significant, ranging from 6-10% (Figure 4d).

While total labor demand peaks between 2040 and 2060 in the baseline scenario and then decreases sharply—mainly due to continuous increases in labor productivity—labor demand rises strongly in all scenarios with an endogenous labor-productivity component and exceeds the baseline level by up to 15%. Even as output begins to decline, the difference in the labor

demand between the damage and the baseline scenarios increases toward the end of the simulation (Figure 4e). In damage scenarios purely driven by exogenous labor productivity improvements, because of changing sectoral productivity levels and production capacities, labor demand first decreases, then increases and eventually falls again. Conversely, due to the increasing heat-related damages impacting the labor supply, in all damage scenarios the maximum pool of labor hours is smaller than in the baseline scenario, with the difference being higher in scenarios with high impacts and higher temperature increases. In the simulations, the adverse effect of deadly heat on the ability to work, rather than the increase in mortality of the working population, proves to be the principal driver behind the reduction in available working hours (Figure 4f). The latter can also be seen in Figure 4g and Figure 4h, which show that climate damages indirectly cause both total deaths and births to increase. The strongest effects are produced in scenarios with high impacts and endogenously evolving labor productivities: by 2100, births and deaths in the high-impact-endogenous-labor-productivity scenario are 48% and 16% higher than in the baseline. Finally, Figure 4f shows how the loss of habitable land increases with increasing climate impacts. As temperature rises faster in scenarios driven only by exogenous labor productivity improvements, the resulting loss of land is higher in those scenarios.

Figure 4: a-b): World GFCF in the baseline (grey (dashed) line), moderate type-A damage (dots), type-B damage (diamonds), type-C damage (stars) and type-ABC damage (yellow (dashed) line) scenarios with (a) endogenously and (b) exogenously evolving labor productivities. Evolution of c) total depreciation, d) share of the food sector's depreciation in total depreciation, e) total labor demand, f) maximum labor supply, g) total births, h) total deaths, i) damage-induced land loss in type-ABC scenarios with low (green), moderate (yellow) and high (blue) impacts as well as with (dots) and without (crosses) endogenously evolving labor productivities.

4. Discussion

We hold that our methodological framework and its implementation in MORDRED constitute a contribution to the loss and damage literature for several reasons. First, rather than modeling damages as impacts on a single parameter—losses to income—we consider the possibility of increased losses in capital stock [45] as well as losses in labor and land productivity. Second, while we distinguish between varying degrees of impact severity across economic sectors, we do not assume that non-weather-related sectors remain unaffected by climate impacts (cf.[13]). Instead, the input-output framework captures spillover effects between more and less vulnerable sectors through the flow of intermediate goods between industries. Third, our damage modeling is sensitive to questions of equity across time and space [45]. We refrain from using discount rates, calculating the social cost of carbon, or fixing intra- or international income distributions *ex ante*. Rather, MORDRED requires scenarios to specify assumptions of future changes in consumption inequalities, thereby avoiding to incorporate questionable ethical assumptions into its default calibration [14]. In the simulated scenarios, which assume moderate convergence between social classes and regions, the forgone consumption under climate change scenarios is higher for richer classes than for poorer ones, and higher in the center than in the periphery (see Figure 2 in the SM), in line with the modeling analysis of De Bruin et al. [1] who indicate that richer households might face higher impacts. However, MORDRED also shows that the periphery and semiperiphery experience stronger increases in mortality rates in response to economic losses, underscoring the importance of coupling life expectancy to changes in per capita consumption (Figure 3 SM). Last, in contrast to optimal growth models like DICE (cf. [13]), economic trajectories in MORDRED are sensitive to climate change impacts, and the model can exhibit collapse dynamics under high damage assumptions. In this context, our simulations highlight the importance of labor productivity assumptions for scenario outcomes, demonstrating that scenarios with endogenously changing labor productivities that consider the link between exergy availability and labor productivity [46] produce development pathways that are more unstable and sensitive to environmental disruptions.

At the same time, assessments of future environmental risks and damages based on MORDRED face several limitations. With respect to parameter values, the quality of our numerical estimates for different damage factors depends on data availability, which is heavily biased toward the Global North. Furthermore, the impossibility of a comprehensive bottom-up reconstruction of climate impacts leads to the exclusion of many impact channels identified in the literature, such as direct mortality increases due to extreme heat [47] or productivity losses in the livestock industry resulting from heat stress on cattle, chicken, and poultry [48], [49]. While this incompleteness likely results in an underestimation of climate impacts, the adopted input-output framework enforces strict production limits once a single sector becomes constrained, which may be overly pessimistic. Regarding the representation of social, environmental, and economic feedback dynamics linked to climate damages, MORDRED currently omits key feedback relationships, such as the influence of climate damages on other systemic risks, including social and geopolitical conflicts [4]. We also intentionally exclude the effects of crossing climate tipping points [50] on economic production, as their quantification remains elusive – a case of *recognized ignorance*, where modelers cannot plausibly develop alternative causal representations [14]. Moreover, given our focus on production-related damage factors, the model does not account for non-economic losses arising from the intrinsic, cultural, religious, or

recreational values of nature [51], [52] which can be highly significant for perceived quality of life.

Thus, while our work enriches existing damage modeling frameworks, future research could extend it by improving parameter estimates, conducting additional sensitivity tests, and incorporating social and political variables. Investigating the possibilities and limits of climate change adaptation [53], particularly for poorer classes and regions, would also yield valuable policy insights. Furthermore, although our focus has been on climate change damages, the methodological framework can be applied to other environmental damages, thereby enhancing the comprehensiveness of environmental impact assessments based on input–output models. This would allow for simulations that explore feedbacks between climate-related and other ecological limits to growth, such as nitrogen pollution [54] and groundwater depletion [55].

While future work may address some of the model’s limitations, *deep uncertainty* [56] and *total ignorance* [14] imply that neither classical risk assessment nor the prediction of societal collapse should be the goal of quantitative loss and damage modeling. As Kareiva and Carranza [51] note, the greatest existential risk from global environmental change lies in our ecological ignorance of the complex feedback dynamics within tightly coupled human–natural systems. We therefore concur with Saltelli et al. [57] on the importance of acknowledging and communicating what is not known, rather than conveying a false sense of certainty.

Conclusion

In this article, we introduced a transparent and structured framework for representing adverse impacts of global environmental change on the economy. We applied this framework to the MORDRED-IAM by introducing a set of climate damage factors and examining their effects on economic developments under different damage scenarios. Unlike neoclassical damage representations in established IAMs, the model’s system-dynamics and input–output foundations produce substantial changes in key economic and technological parameters once climate damages are activated. This highlights both the threat climate change poses to economic growth and the urgency of strengthening international cooperation on climate governance. While we argue that MORDRED yields quantitative projections that are ‘less wrong’ than those of optimal-growth IAMs, it remains essential to acknowledge the unknowable, unpredictable positive and negative surprises waiting in the future.

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